

Absorption Spectra of Mixtures of Dilute Solutions of Copper Sulphate and Sodium Sulphite in the Red and the Ultra-violet.

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It is well known that a solution of sodium sulphite undergoes oxidation in the dark in contact with the oxygen of the atmosphere. This oxidation is also accelerated by light. The problem has recently been investigated by Backström (*Medd. k. Vetenskapsad. Nobel Inst.*, 1927, 6, 16).

Titoff observed long ago that a copper salt, in small traces even, is a powerful positive catalyst for this oxidation in the dark. In view of this observation of Titoff it was felt worthwhile investigating quantitatively the absorption spectra of mixtures of dilute solutions of copper sulphate and sodium sulphite and comparing the values of the extinctions coefficients of the mixtures with the sum of those of the constituents.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The absorptions were measured in the red with the help of a König-Marten spectrophotometer. Lines of quartz mercury-lamp were used in calibrating the instrument.

It was noticed that on mixing a solution of $M/10$ -sodium sulphite with $M/500$ -copper sulphate which had practically no absorption in the visible, a visible blue colour was developed and that the colour disappeared within a very short interval of its first appearance. Hence, the following precaution was necessary:—Since the mixture is rapidly oxidised in the air, carbon dioxide was passed through the solutions of sodium sulphite and copper sulphate before they were mixed. Carbon dioxide was also passed into the reaction cell for a considerable period of time. Each component of the mixture was separately introduced into the reaction cell and the cell was closed immediately and sealed with soft sealing wax.

The strength of the sodium sulphite in the mixture was at least ten times greater than that of the copper sulphate.

The minimum strength of copper sulphate should be $M/1000$ in the mixture and that of sodium sulphite should not be below $M/100$.

Results.

Size of reaction cell = 4 cm. × 4 cm. × 2 cm.

(The cell was placed in the normal position.)

Wave-length of the region investigated = 655 $\mu\mu$. Spectrophotometer readings*

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|--|-----|-----|
| (1) Zero reading | ... | 29° |
| (2) With 10 c.c. of water in the reaction cell | ... | 28° |
| (3) With 10 c.c. of M/500-CuSO ₄ soln. in the reaction cell | ... | 28° |

Mixtures.

(A) 5 c.c. of M/500-CuSO₄ soln. and 5 c.c. of M/10-Na₂SO₃ soln..

Date.	Hour.	Readings.
5-4-29.	2-10 P.M.	20° (a)
	3-10 ..	22°
	4-10 ..	24°
6-4-29.	6 ..	26° (a')

$$(a) \log I_0/I_t = 0.1462$$

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(B) 5 c.c. of M/500-CuSO₄ soln. and 5 c.c. of M/20-Na₂SO₃ soln.
Spectrophotometer readings = 25° (b)

$$(b) \log I_0/I_t = 0.0493.$$

(C) 5 c.c. of M/500-CuSO₄ soln. and 5 c.c. of M/40-Na₂SO₃ soln.
Spectrophotometer reading = 27° (c)

$$(c) \log I_0/I_t = 0.0158.$$

The following data were obtained in an attempt to find out whether any exaltation in the value of the extinction coefficients of the mixture of copper sulphate and sodium sulphite over the sum of those of the constituents took place in the ultra-violet.

Wave-length	log I ₀ /I _t for	log I ₀ /I _t for	log I ₀ /I _t for
	2961	2770	2600
M/10-Na ₂ SO ₃	—	0.1	0.45
M/500-CuSO ₄	0.15	0.2	0.25
Mixture	0.15	0.3	0.7

It will be seen from data given above that there is no exaltation in the value of the extinction coefficients of the mixture.

Discussion.

It will be noticed that there is a very marked increase in the extinction coefficient of the mixtures of the dilute solution of copper sulphate and sodium sulphite in the red region. In fact, $M/500$ -copper sulphate appears almost colourless to the eye in layers of 1 cm. thickness whereas on mixing with sodium sulphite solution a very perceptible greenish blue colouration is developed. This increase in absorption coefficient in the red must be due to an unstable intermediate complex formed by the action of copper sulphate with sodium sulphite. This complex decomposes fairly quickly and the greenish blue colour disappears after sometime.

It is curious that the mixtures of copper sulphate and sodium sulphite solutions do not show any exaltation in the extinction coefficient in the ultra-violet between $260\mu\mu$ and $296\mu\mu$. It is very probable that inertness of copper sulphate, so far as the photochemical oxidation of sodium sulphite is concerned, is related to the absence of the exaltation effect in the ultra-violet. It is also probable that the catalytic action of copper sulphate on the 'dark' oxidation of sodium sulphite may find its explanation in the pronounced exaltation of extinction coefficients of the mixtures of these two reactants in the red and infra-red. Further investigation on this subject is in progress.

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